

POLICY BRIEF

EMPOWER LOCAL COMMUNITIES AND END ILLEGAL DEFORESTATION

How the European Commission can leverage communities' knowledge to enhance the EUDR benchmarking and drive real progress on defeating deforestation.

In a Nutshell

Deforestation continues to accelerate globally, yet policy action to date has yet to fully deliver. Citizen generated data collected by local communities, including Indigenous peoples, who monitor forests daily can complement official data, provide documentation to expose fraud in value chains, and improve the success of regulations such as the EUDR. To ensure impact, the European Commission should consider citizen generated data and insights into country-risk benchmarking.

Policy Context

In December 2023, the EU passed the Deforestation-free products Regulation (EUDR) to shield EU supply chains from deforestation-related harm. Yet it is already being challenged at its core, highlighting the need to protect it and ensure it delivers its intended impact. Art.29 of the EUDR employs a country benchmarking system to target countries exposed to the risk of deforestation, guiding due diligence and encouraging systemic change.

The first classification (May 2025), based primarily on the FAO Forest Resources Assessment data (FRA), drew criticism for failing to reflect risks, due to reliance on national aggregates and political considerations. The updated list is expected in May 2026, underscoring the challenge of achieving reliable, actionable benchmarking.

Policy Challenge

The classification system draws on both quantitative and qualitative data: deforestation rates, agricultural expansion, commodity production trends, governance quality, and compliance with international agreements. Producing a reliable benchmark on this basis is a complex task, further aggravated by trade and geopolitical considerations.

How can the European Commission ensure that the classification truly reflects risk in value chains? The challenge is critical.

A benchmarking mechanism that does not match actual risks undermines the EUDR's objectives and its capacity to drive meaningful business, social and environmental change.

Local communities can make a difference

Article 29(3) of the EUDR requires the European Commission to consider “... the latest scientific evidence and internationally recognised sources ...” when assessing deforestation and forest degradation. These sources, such as the FAO FRA dataset used in May 2025, rely predominantly on government reporting.

The FAO provides guidelines on what and how to report; however, countries will often use their own methods. This presents two main weaknesses:

- National aggregates can mask local deforestation hotspots.
- Some countries may intentionally provide misleading or unverifiable data.

Data generated by local communities can provide data where authorities lack the capacity or will to monitor and report on deforestation and degradation. The benchmark will reflect reality once this knowledge and the way local communities are treated by public authorities are duly considered in the assessment.

Course of Action

While recognizing the complexity and political sensitivity of deforestation, more4nature urges the European Commission, ahead of the next classification review, to broaden the interpretation of “latest scientific evidence and internationally recognised sources” under Article 29(3) of the EUDR.

The FAO FRA is robust and valuable for global comparisons but is updated only every 5 years and lacks sufficient granularity to reflect localised deforestation.

Benchmarking should therefore also draw on the University of Maryland/GLAD that provides

high resolution, real-time monitoring and captures unexpected or local deforestation events. It is one of the core scientific engines behind Global Forest Watch, an independent, publicly accessible satellite monitoring identifying local hotspots.

Verified and acknowledged data streams from local communities are ground-level evidence that can fill gaps in government reporting. Integrating such data would enhance EUDR risk assessments and support NGOs, companies, and authorities in protecting forests that sustain life on the planet.

Voices on the ground

📍 Ukraine

Vasyl Losiuk
Research associate at the National Nature Park Hutsulshchyna

“Currently, the risk of illegal logging in Ukraine is quite high. [...] However, it should be noted that over the past year, law enforcement agencies of our state have strongly begun to fight corruption in the forestry sector. In my opinion, information from citizens about illegal logging should be included in internationally recognized data sources if this data is verified.”

Reach out to us!

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